

The Effectiveness of the Program to Improve Undergraduate Qualifications through Dual Mode System for Islamic Elementary School Teachers in West Nusa Tenggara, East Nusa Tenggara and Bali, Indonesia

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 04, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: September 06, 2021</p> <p>Keywords : Evaluation, DMS Program, Undergraduate Qualification, CIPPO Model, Islamic Elementary School Teachers</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5476107</p>	<p><i>This study aims to identify the effectiveness of undergraduate qualification improvement program for Madrasah Ibtidaiyah (Islamic Elementary School-IES) teachers and Islamic Religious Education (Islamic Education: IE) Teachers through Dual Mode System (DMS) for West Nusa Tenggara, East Nusa Tenggara, and Bali at Mataram State Islamic University (UIN Mataram, Indonesia). The target determined in this study is seen from five components: (1) context, (2) input, (3) process, (4) product, and (5) outcome. This study used a qualitative research approach, with operational guidelines for the implementation of DMS program from Directorate of Islamic Higher Education (DIKTIS). This study categorized as an evaluation program by using a case study method that focused on the form of the program, the implementation of policies, or the concept of research. The research design model applied was CIPPO model from Stufflebeam and Gilbert Sax. Based on the evaluation of the context, DMS program at Mataram State Islamic University had a clear juridical foundation and showed the high needs of the community in supporting the implementation of the DMS undergraduate program (87%). Based on the evaluation of the input as a whole, it has run well and matched the input characteristics of the standard DMS program (91.61%). Meanwhile, the process evaluation revealed that the process components had met the characteristics of the standard DMS program process (60%). The results of the program evaluation on the product aspect also showed extraordinary achievements (100%).</i></p>

Introduction

Background of the Study

Adequate human resources are a strength that Indonesian should have in the era of globalization, information and technology, especially when dealing with the phase of the Asean Economic Community (AEC). However, it turns out that the Indonesian nation has not ready with adequate human resources or is still concerning (Suyanto & Abbas, 2004). Whereas, educational institutions that are expected to be able to produce good human resources are still in low quality (Nurrahmah, 2014). Thus, great attention is needed in order to create a quality education model, especially science education and technological development (Tilaar, 2002).

In order to achieve educational development that is able to contribute in improving the quality of human resources, there are three main requirements, namely: building facilities, adequate and quality books, also teachers and professional staff (LKM UNJ Creative Team, 2011; Mulyasa, 2005). Further, to achieve educational development can contribute to improve the quality of human resources, there are three main requirements, namely: building facilities, adequate and quality books, also teachers and professional staff (LKM UNJ Creative Team, 2011; Mulyasa, 2005). Teachers play a big role in creating good human resources. Observing the regulations for education personnel in Indonesia, teachers hold professional positions at the levels of primary, secondary and early childhood education in the formal which are appointed in accordance with the laws and regulations (Law No.14 of 2005: Article 2 Paragraph 1). Acknowledgment of the teachers' position as professionals as referred above is proofed by teacher certification (Law No. 14 of 2005: Article 2 Paragraph 2), further followed by the provision of professional award incentives (Sarimaya, 2008). This provision applied to all teachers.

In Indonesia, Islamic Educational School in the last decades of the 20th century AD was positioned as alternative educational institutions (Subhan, 2012). However, Islamic School (Elementary, Junior, and Senior high school) in terms of teaching staff/teachers still have a lot of weaknesses both in terms of quantity and quality of teacher education that mostly they are under S1 Level. Thus, the Ministry of Religion of Republic of Indonesia assists teachers. So that way, the Ministry of Religion gets state teachers to help those Islamic Educational Schools. In addition, the Ministry of Religion strives to improve teacher education qualifications

through scholarship programs for those who meet the requirements to continue to the higher education levels such as university.

The number of teachers in the Ministry of Religion who taught in Islamic Elementary School, Islamic Religious Education, Islamic Junior High School (MTs) and Islamic Senior High School (MA), since 2008-2009 school year were 524,543 people (Fattah, 2018). As for the details, the number of teachers at Islamic elementary schools categorized as public schools (MIN) in that academic year were 1,686 (7.55%) and private elementary schools (MIS) as many as 20,782 people (92.5%). The numbers of teachers at State Junior High Schools (MTsN) were 1,437 people (9.7%) and teachers at Private Junior High Schools (MTs) were 13,320 people (90.3%). The number of teachers at State Islamic Senior High School were 758 people (11.8%), while teachers Private Islamic Senior High School (MAS) were 5,657 (88.2%) (the Ministry of Religious Affairs of the Republic of Indonesia, 2009). From those data, Islamic Elementary School and Islamic religious education teachers (in Indonesia) rank first in terms of quantity.

The Ministry of Religion has innovated this program so that it does not interfere with the implementation of every teacher's daily duties. Since 2009/2010 academic year, Directorate General of Islamic Studies of the Ministry of Religion has organized an undergraduate academic qualification program for Islamic elementary school teachers and Islamic religious education (PAI) teachers in public schools using Dual Mode System (DMS) approach. However, the program faced a number of obstacles that hinder the successful implementation of the program.

Furthermore, to find out the success and failure of this program, it is necessary to conduct an evaluative study, especially the teacher qualification upgrading program through DMS organized by Provinces of West Nusa Tenggara, East Nusa Tenggara, and Bali which in its implementation takes place at Mataram State Islamic University. The research design model used is the CIPP Stufflebeam evaluation model refined by Gilbert Sax (University of Washington) by adding a yield component (O), so that it becomes a CIPPO model.

Research Questions

Based on the background of the study above, the researcher formulates some research questions below:

1. In order to evaluate the success of the program from the aspect of context, the following questions were analyzed:
 - a. Does the implementation of Islamic School and Islamic Education Teacher qualification Improvement Program through Dual Mode System (DMS) at Ministry of Religion of West Nusa Tenggara, East Nusa Tenggara and Bali provinces based on the DMS UIN Mataram have a clear formal basis?
 - b. Does DMS program represent the needs of the community / Islamic school teachers and Islamic education teachers in general schools?
2. In order to evaluate the success of the program from the input aspect, the following questions were examined:
 - a. Is DMS student recruitment system implemented in accordance with the procedures set by the Ministry of Religion of the Republic of Indonesia?
 - b. Is the system for determining educational staff (lecturers) and education staff (secretariat staff) DMS implemented in accordance with the procedures established by Indonesian Ministry of Religion?
 - c. Are curriculum policies, course distribution, and schedules identified prior to program implementation?
 - d. Are the syllabus and course units identified before lecture?
 - e. Are the lecture modules distributed suitable for each subject?
 - f. Does the DMS program utilize infrastructure (learning resources) to achieve its goals?
 - g. Is there an adequate budget / finance according to the intended purpose?
 - h. Is there sufficient stakeholder / community support to support the DSM program?
3. In order to evaluate the success of the program from the process aspect, the following questions were identified:
 - a. Is DMS lecture well documented?
 - b. Do DMS learning activities go on through adequate learning planning?
 - c. Do learning activities take place by maximizing the interaction of the parties involved in the learning process?
 - d. Do monitoring and evaluation (MONEV) activities in the learning process go on according to their function?
4. To evaluate the success of the program from the product aspect, the following questions are asked: Are the learning outcomes of the DMS Program students in based on the objectives of (products) set?
5. To see the success of the program from the outcome aspect, the following questions were examined:
 - a. Are the DMS program graduates able to prepare lessons plan?
 - b. Do DMS Program graduates have the same teaching skills as in Professional Tools / Teacher Training?
 - c. Do DMS Program graduates get a higher mandate/assignment (formal category)?(result)?

Theoretical Framework

Concept of Program Evaluation

In the *Essentials of Educational Evaluation* book by Wand and Brown (2004) evaluation is defined as an action or process to determine value on something. However, World Health Organization (2000) defines evaluation as the attitude of constantly questioning and obtaining information. Based on this definition, educational evaluation can be interpreted as an action or process in order to determine the axiology or value of everything in the world of education or anything that has a relationship with the world of education. Schriener historically in the early development of the science of evaluation was defined as 'assessing the value or benefit of something' as cited in Fitzpatrick, Sanders, and Worthen (2004). The Committee on Standards for Educational Evaluation, that is called evaluation means a study designed and conducted to help multiple audiences to assess the benefits and value of objects (Rogers, 2005).

Program evaluation deals with the systematic collection of information related to program activities, characteristics, and results to make program assessments, increase program effectiveness, and/or inform decisions about future program development (Chapel, 2000). While, according to Chen (2005) program evaluation refers to 'the application of evaluation approaches, techniques, and knowledge to assess systematically and improve program planning, implementation, and effectiveness. From Chen's definition, it is explained that program evaluation is a form of activity in order to apply various approaches, techniques, and evaluation knowledge to assess systematically and effort to improve the quality of planning, implementation, and effectiveness of a program. Stufflebeam and Shinkfield (2007) state that evaluation is a systematic assessment of the benefits, value, honesty, worthiness, safety, significance, and or equity of an object. Stufflebeam definition describes that evaluation is 'a systematic assessment of an object of benefit, value, honesty, appropriateness, security, meaning, and or fairness. Besides, Spaulding (2008), supports program evaluation as a program to determine value and make recommendations for program improvement and success. Meanwhile, Sudjana (2006) sees program evaluation as a systematic activity to collect, process, analyze, and present data as input for decision making.

Whereas, according to Malcolm and Provus in Tayibnapi (2008) postulates evaluation as a form of difference that exists with standards in an effort to determine whether there is a difference or no. Further implementative explanation from Mugiadi in Sudjana (2006) explains that evaluation is a program that have a purpose to gather information about a program, activity or project. The information obtained is useful for making decisions, like to improve the program, perfect the next program activity, stop an activity, or disseminate ideas that underlie a program or activity. Besides, Lazwardi (2017) underlines that various discussions on evaluation theory can be emphasized that evaluation is an activity of gathering information that is useful for decision making and as a measure of the extent to which goals can be achieved. From those definitions of program evaluation above, it can be concluded that program evaluation is the activity of gathering information, analyzing, and assigning value systematically based on the criteria or standards set for decision making. In addition, program evaluation has many uses, including for program improvement; accountability and decision making; assessment of achievement, value, and significance; and also to "promote social welfare" (Gargani & Miller, 2016).

Basic Concept of Dual Mode System (DMS)

IES and IE undergraduate teacher qualification upgrading program in schools is an educational program specifically designed for service teachers within the Ministry of Religion. This program is implemented by Islamic Higher Education (IHE), whose teaching and learning process uses DMS approach through the integration of conventional learning systems (face to face on campus) and independent learning systems.

The implementation of this program is based on the mandate of Law Number 14 of 2005 concerning Teachers, Lecturers, and Government Regulation Number 19 of 2005 concerning National Education Standards. According to PP. 19 of 2005 Article 29 paragraph (2), a teacher (IES or IE school) must have at least a Bachelor or Diploma IV academic qualification, as well as a professional certificate. Therefore, Directorate General of Islamic Education of the Ministry of Religion of Republic Indonesia for academic year 2008/2009 held a bachelor academic qualification for IES and IE Teachers in Schools using Dual Mode System approach.

The Purposes and Competencies of DMS Program Graduation

The implementation of Undergraduate Academic Qualification program for IES and IE teachers in schools through DMS aims to:

- 1) Resulting in graduates who have a Bachelor of Islamic Education academic qualifications for IES and IE teachers in schools.

- 2) Providing education services to improve qualifications for IES and IE teacher schools that have passed the PGA (Islamic religion teacher education program at the high school level) and two-year diplomas according to legal guidelines.

The competence of graduates of undergraduate academic qualification program for IES and IE teachers in schools with DMS approach tends to be graduates who have pedagogical personal, professional, and social competence.

DMS Program Curriculum

The structure of the undergraduate curriculum for IES and IE teachers in schools that use DMS approach consists of basic subjects, major courses, and other subjects, with a total of 144-150 credits. The credit unit and the length of the program that the student must take are based on the educational background of the prospective student by referring to the Decree of the Minister of National Education No. 234 / U / 2000, as illustrated in table 1 below.

Table 1. Credits and length of study for Undergraduate Qualification Improvement Program through DMS at Mataram State Islamic University

Educational Background	Credits	Length
Senior High School	144-160	8-10 semester
One Year Diploma in Education	110-120	6-8 semester
Two Years Diploma in Education	70-80	4-6 semester
Three Years Diploma in Education	40-50	2-4 Semester

Teaching and Learning Process Dual Mode System (DMS)

The teaching and learning process of DMS program is used a "dual mode" approach through a combination of face-to-face learning systems and autonomous learning systems. Face-to-face learning is carried out in order to strengthen student to master material presented in independent learning material through a series of direct meetings between students and lecturers on a scheduled basis. The learning material presented includes: (1) The students get difficulties to understand concepts of learning materials in independent learning (2) the application and problem solving that arise from the material contained in the independent study material; (3) suggestion for completing assignments that students must do in individual and group capacities, and (4) suggestion for practicum implementation that must be done by students either individually or in groups. Face-to-face learning activities are done by several methods such as: a) Lectures and questionnaires, b) Class or group discussions, c) Guidance for demonstrative activities and practicum, and d) Coaching for task completion.

Independent learning is learning that runs out using material for independent learning purposes called modules. The technique is that at the beginning of the lecture, the lecturer explains the learning method using modules. In the module also explains how to study it in more detail according to the characteristics of each course. Furthermore, in independent learning process, students can study modules, either individually or in groups.

Selected Evaluation Model

Stufflebeam (2002) states "The CIPP model is based on the view that the most important objective of evaluation is not to prove, but to improve". In line with the research questions that have been formulated in this study that aims to evaluate comprehensively IES and EI Teacher Qualification Improvement Program through DMS at Mataram State Islamic University (UIN Mataram, Indonesia) comprehensively, the components of the context, input, process, product and impact/influence, hence the CIPPO model was chosen. The CIPPO model is a development of the CIPP evaluation model that was refined by Gilbert Sax's Stufflebeam by adding a yield component (O) or outcome aspect, so that it becomes a CIPPO model (Arikunto & Jabar, 2008, p. 45). The CIPPO evaluation model was chosen in this study to evaluate comprehensively the IES and EI teacher qualification improvement program through DMS at Mataram Islamic State University. The output in this study put the focus on the impact of this program on DMS graduates, such as (1) the ability of DMS alumni teachers in preparing lesson plans based on instruments provided by the Ministry of Religion, (2) the capability of DMS alumni teachers in teaching based on the apparatus of the Ministry of Religion Republic Indonesia, and (3) maximizing the level of empowerment at institution/Islamic School in charge.

In addition, The CIPPO model was also selected because it includes summative evaluation, which is carried out after a program is completed (ex-post), such as (1) the ability of DMS alumni teachers to prepare lessons plan based on instruments provided by the Ministry of Religion, (2) the ability of DMS alumni teachers in teaching based on instruments of the Ministry of Religion Republic Indonesia, and (3) maximizing the level of empowerment in institutions/Islamic School/ official schools.

Context evaluation according to Fernandes (1984) includes analysis of problems related to the program environment or objective conditions to be implemented. Input evaluation is an evaluation that can help to

manage decisions, determine existing resources, taken alternatives, the kind of plans and strategies that are needed to achieve the needs, and the procedures to achieve them (Tayibnapis, 2008).

According to Arikunto (2013), the evaluation process refers to the extent to which activities in the program have been carried out as planned. Product evaluation must assess the desired goals and desired results, both positive and negative (Stufflebeam & Shinkfield, 2007). Outcome assessment is a consequence of an intangible outcome of a program (Smith, 1996; Kröger et al., 1998).

Methods

Approaches, Methods, and Design of Research Models

When this study seen from the type of data in the form of narration, images and text, this research is included as qualitative research. Another then thus, the method uses was analytical descriptions, this research is also categorized into qualitative research, means research that requires a depth of analytical appreciation of the interactions between concepts being studied empirically. The process of collecting data in this study used several techniques, including; (1) observation, both participatory and non-participatory observation, (2) In-depth interviews and structured interviews, and (3) Documentation study techniques. Therefore, the approach used in this research utilizes a qualitative approach, with the criteria for operational guidelines for the implementation of DMS Program set by the Directorate of Islamic Higher Education (DIHE) of the Ministry of Religion Republic Indonesia. Those guidelines are in accordance with the Government Regulation of Republic of Indonesia Number 19 of 2005 concerning 8 National Education Standards consisting of; (1) content standards, (2) process standards, (3) competency standards for graduates, (4) standards for educators and educational personnel, (5) standards for facilities and infrastructure, (6) management standards, (7) financing standards, and (8) educational assessment standards. This study put the focus to identify where the goal achievement has been achieved.

This study is a program evaluation using a case study method that focused on a single selected and attempted phenomenon to be understood in depth, apart from other phenomena. This phenomenon can be in the form of programs, policy implementation, or concepts (Sukmadinata, 2010; Yim et al., 2020). In this study, the program evaluated is a program to increase the qualification of the Bachelor through DMS. The research design model used is the CIPP Stufflebeam evaluation model which was refined by Gilbert Sax (University of Washington) by adding a yield component (O) or outcome aspect, so that it becomes a CIPPO model. This CIPPO evaluation model was chosen in this study to comprehensively evaluate the IES and IE teacher qualification improvement program through the DMS UIN Mataram with the research design shown in Figure 1 below:

Figure 1. Research design for program evaluation of DMS in Mataram State Islamic University

Instrument Validity and Reliability

There are three types of instruments to collect data used in this study; (1) document study, (2) interview guide, and (3) questionnaire which is divided into five stages of evaluation: context, input, process, product, and outcome. Before the research instrument was used, content and construct validation was carried out. The non-test instrument used to measure attitudes has met the validity of the construct. Meanwhile, to test the validity of the construct, expert (panelist) assessments regarding the instruments that have been prepared (Sugiyono, 2009; Mishra & Alok, 2017), are reliable.

Instrument validation was done by 5 experts and analyzed using V validation index formula (Aiken, 1980), and inter-rater reliability analysis (Djaali & Mulyono, 2008). After revised based on expert recommendations, the instrument (questionnaire) was tested for reliability, done with Internal Consistency, like the test instrument (questionnaire) was only done once (Sugiyono, 2009; Mishra & Alok, 2017). Then the

validity of the data obtained was analyzed using the Pearson Product Moment correlation formula. Furthermore, the reliability of the instrument items (questionnaire) test results was valid, then analyzed by Cronbach Alpha formula using SPSS application, and r count was obtained for the questionnaire manager of 0.987; the lecturer r count questionnaire was 0.966, and the student r count questionnaire was 0.954. It was found that the calculated r value is greater than t table. According to Sugiyono (2012) and Mishra & Alok (2017), the correlation coefficient value is between 0.80 - 1.00, meaning that the correlation coefficient is high and it can be directly used for research.

Data Collection and Analysis Procedures

The data used in this study were secondary data and primary data. Primary data was in the form of data collected directly from teachers or lecturers, students, university leaders, DMS managers, the Ministry of Religion (central / district / city), and Islamic Schools or school principals / vice principals that becomes respondents. Secondary data is data obtained from existing data in the form of policies, operational guidelines or standardization of the implementation of the DMS program at Mataram State Islamic University.

The qualitative data collection techniques used was interviews and guidelines, open questionnaires, and document analysis. Meanwhile, quantitative data collection used closed questionnaires and guidelines. In accordance with the characteristics of qualitative research, data collection is considered complete, or it is stopped if the data collected is sufficient and does not change or reaches a saturation point.

There were two kinds of data analysis techniques used in this research, namely descriptive statistics and qualitative data analysis. Qualitative data analysis using the model of Miles and Huberman (1992) consists of three flow activities or processes that occur simultaneously were; (1) data reduction, (2) data presentation, and (3) drawing conclusions / verification.

Findings and Discussion

Context Evaluation

Based on the results of this study, the evaluation of undergraduate qualification improvement program through DMS in context aspects at Mataram State Islamic University included 2 main points; (1) the legality component of implementing DMS and the existence of DMS Program at Mataram State Islamic University, and (2) the emergence of an urgent need for the community or teachers in the program. This study revealed that all components of the context have a clear legal-judicial basis and showed the high needs of the societies/teachers for the program. On that basis, what needs to be improved is the problem of equitable and broad access to education for Islamic School teachers to enable them to get a bachelor's degree based on their scientific field and teaching duties.

This program was an implementation of the Constitution 1945 which mandates the basic rights of citizens regarding education as outlined in Law Number 14 of 2005 concerning Teachers and Lecturers. The National Education System Law is strengthened by Government Regulation no. 19 of 2005 concerning National Education Standards Article 29 paragraph (2), which states that a teacher (IES and IE teachers in schools) must have at least a four-year Bachelor's degree or diploma as a requirement for academic qualifications. Another legal aspect that forms the basis of this DMS program is the Circular Decree of the Minister of Religion of the Republic of Indonesia Number 179 of 2008 concerning the Implementation of the Islamic School Teacher Graduate Qualification Program in Indonesia.

Input Evaluation

DMS program input evaluation which includes components of students, lecturers, administrators and administrative staff, curriculum, syllabus / SAP, lecture modules, budget, availability of facilities and infrastructure, as well as support for community participation, showed that overall input components already existed, run well and met the standard input characteristics of DMS program at Mataram State Islamic University. This can be seen in the student affairs component, the implementation of DMS undergraduate student recruitment is running smoothly, but there were some weaknesses in terms of the administrative selection element which seems less careful. Another problem that arises was related to student grouping. Referring to the ideal concept, the class for Islamic Elementary School Education Teachers (IE) is only intended for students who are PGMI teachers. Likewise, Islamic Religious Education Teacher (IES) class in public schools is actually intended for those who were assigned as Islamic religion teachers in public schools. However, the facts show that IE class (136 people) was filled with 75 college students with IES teacher status. Similarly, in ES class (374 people), there were 45 college students who become IE teachers.

In terms of lecturer component, DMS Manager at Faculty of Tarbiyah and Teacher Training, Mataram State Islamic University has tried to implement the right work mechanism in the recruitment, selection and placement of lecturers. However, it must be admitted that the existing implementation is not perfect and cannot accommodate all the interests of lecturers who want to teach at DMS. This occurs because consideration of

academic qualifications and competencies, or even less 'quality' experience to be accommodated as a lecturer at DMS.

Based on the analysis of DMS program documents at Mataram State Islamic University, lecturers can be grouped into 2 categories, (1) permanent lecturers and (2) non-permanent lecturers. The data depicted that for "permanent lecturers", the details are 18 lecturers with doctoral academic qualifications (S3), and 113 lecturers with master qualifications (S2). Meanwhile, for "non-permanent lecturers", there is only 1 lecturer with a doctoral qualification (S3), 15 lecturers with a master qualification (S2), and 5 lecturers with an undergraduate qualification (S1). Details of DMS teacher / lecturer qualifications can be illustrated in the table below.

Table 2. Number and education level of DMS Program at Mataram State Islamic University (UIN Mataram, Indonesia)

No	Classification	Educational Qualification			Total
		Undergraduate Program	Master	Doctoral	
1	Permanent lecturer	-	113	18	131
2	Non-Permanent Lecturer	5 *	15	1	21

*. Recruited from the local religious office

From above table, it can be seen that the number of "Permanent Lecturers" at Mataram State Islamic University who teaches in DMS Undergraduate Program reached 91.61%, while "Non-Permanent Lecturers" only reached 8.39%.

Regarding administrators and administrative staff, it is necessary to consider the integration of scientific posture nomenclature between departments (programs) that were opened with the program leader, so that the credo of the right person for the right job is well selected. In addition, the coordinator of the program must be able to mobilize all available resources to move simultaneously the program wheels more effectively and efficiently.

In the structure of the curriculum content, it was found that the curriculum model for students of DMS Mataram State Islamic University was a specialization model curriculum, which idealizes certain external competencies supported by instrumental / secondary skills to support their main abilities as the output of the Islamic Education institution. The curriculum structure had fulfilled the standards in the preparation of higher education curricula and can meet the pedagogical abilities of students as professional teacher candidates after obtaining a bachelor degree.

Meanwhile, the numbers of teachers who have to take part in the qualification upgrade program, but have a variety of educational backgrounds and experiences of potential participants, it is possible to convert credits or Recognition of the Prior Learning (RPL), in the form of educational qualifications, teaching experience, professional training, and work performance. It had an objective as a form of appreciation to teachers who were able to become "credit earnings" in completing the teacher qualification improvement program. To carry out the lecture conversion, the management of DMS Mataram State Islamic University has developed an academic task force team that really understands the anatomy of Tarbiyah and Teacher Training Faculty curriculum.

Normatively, the conversion carried out by the Manager was well enough, but still needed improvement. In the future, if there is a similar program, the manager must accommodate the experience and activities of college students (in position: teacher) which can be recognized as equivalent to the course that they study.

Regarding the arrangement of syllabus and lesson plans (course schedules), based on the results of the analysis of questionnaires distributed to DMS lecturer and verification of documentation, it described that the majority (97.82%) of DMS teaching staff at Mataram Islamic University condition the lecture process by compiling a syllabus and lesson plans. The analysis also shows that the lecturer attendance rate is very high (91% for West Nusa Tenggara, 97% for East Nusa Tenggara, and 98% for Bali). Likewise, student attendance (93% for West Nusa Tenggara, 97% for East Nusa Tenggara and 98% for Bali).

The percentage above showed that there were a little proportion of lecturers who did not compile a syllabus with the assumption that the 'ready-use' module provides details of 'what' and 'how' the learning process should be taught. The syllabus in the context of DMS was not a complicated thing because the preparation of the syllabus only required adjustments to the modules distributed by the Management, Directorate of Islamic Religious Education of Republic Indonesia. For this reason, in preparing the syllabus, the duties of DMS lecturers were quite simple, such as review, add, or reduce the syllabus according to the context and needs of students.

In the module component, most of the DMS lecture modules were prepared by Directorate General of Islamic Education (DIRJEN PENDIS) team and the modules were compiled by lecturers at Mataram State Islamic University who were technically and qualitatively qualified and representative to support the lecture process ideal, especially in the aspect of module substance.

The contents of the module have shown the correlation between the sections, including the scope of the legibility aspect. The layout of module was quite well arranged, the use of Bahasa, the demands of sentence formulation, the integrity of the description, and the use of terms in the module were sufficient. Although it must be admitted quantitatively the physical appearance of module duplicated by Management was complained by DMS students. For instance, they complained about the physical appearance, the page placement is not sequential and even some pages are missing. Likewise, complaints about the color of the module are blurry, the binding is not correct, and the appearance is less interesting. However, the problem of module display is less attractive, maybe less substantive because the Manager has facilitated the module to support quality, meaningful, and meaningful lectures for DMS students as a subject.

In the aspect of budget, DMS financial report data documentation was strengthened by DMS Mataram State Islamic University that every one semester, each student is budgeted at Rp. 3,700,000, - (three million seven hundred thousand rupiah) allocated for (1) student registration fee of Rp. 100,000, - (one hundred thousand rupiah), (2) indirect costs Rp. 2,300,000, - (two million three hundred thousand rupiah) consisting of a tuition fee of Rp. 400,000, - (four hundred thousand rupiah), BPP fee of Rp. 1,600,000, - (one million six hundred thousand rupiah), laboratory fee of Rp. 200,000, - (two hundred thousand rupiah), monitoring and evaluation costs Rp. 100,000, - (one hundred thousand rupiah), and (3) direct costs of Rp. 600,000, - (six hundred thousand rupiah).

The lack of funds for the implementation of DMS, as reported by DMS Core Management, was due to the very high the use of the BPP budget consisting of lecturers' transport costs, rental and maintenance costs for facilities and infrastructure, as well as operational costs in various operational areas.

In this context, the Ministry of Religion Center (KEMENAG RI) as the Budget Holder must be observant in arranging budget schemes based on regional mapping by taking into account the area and the difficulty of the locus and not only based on the standardized calculation of 'distance'.

The learning facilities at the DMS Center were quite adequate, but these facilities were rarely used optimally, such as laboratories were seldom used for teaching and learning processes. In fact, there were no learning practices that show educational interactions between lecturers and students in the laboratory. Likewise, the number of DMS student visits to the library of Mataram State Islamic University is also not optimal, so that there are several DMS courses requiring the use of other learning sources as a method of increasing the professionalism of prospective teachers.

In the aspect of society's participation or support, Mataram State Islamic University did not collaborate with other universities in the field of Program Management (as a lecturer). Partnerships were built in the form / context of lecture facilities and infrastructure with a rental system, both with universities, Islamic schools/schools, and related agencies. The universities involved in this collaboration model were Hamzanwadi Islamic Institute of East Lombok (WNT), Samawa University, Sumbawa (WNT), and STAI Al-Amin Dompu (WNT). Further, Islamic Schools that are used as lecture locations are Mataram Model Islamic Middle School (MAN 2), Praya Lombok Tengah Model Islamic Junior High School (MTsN-WNT), Bima Islamic Senior High School (MAN 1 Kota Bima-WNT) and Kupang Islamic High School (MAN Kupang-ENT).

Based on the results of the analysis of the questionnaire distributed to respondents who manage DMS program, the role of the community and family in supporting the implementation of DMS program was known that 6% said it was very good, 46% was good, 35% was average, 9% was poor and 4% was very poor. (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Community and Family role in supporting the implementation of undergraduate DMS in Mataram State Islamic University

Based on the results of document studies, interviews, and questionnaire analysis, it was known that the community and family played a major role in supporting the DMS program. Support and partnerships that built was in the form of lecture facilities with a rental system, both with universities, Islamic schools, and related agencies. In addition, graduates or alumni participated in socialization, student selection, and development of student professional skills through Integrated Participatory Field Work Practices, as well as providing a place for research locations (thesis).

Process Evaluation

Program evaluation on the aspect of process which includes lecture administration, lecture activities, lecture assessments, and Monitoring and Evaluation (MONEV) showed that all process components had run well and met the characteristics of DMS Program process standard.

Regarding the implementation of lectures, based on document studies, interviews, and questionnaires, it is known that DMS lecture schedules refer to the academic calendar that has been prepared by DMS Program Manager of Mataram State Islamic University (UIN Mataram) and the academic calendar of Directorate of Islamic Higher Education, Ministry of Religion. The aspects evaluated in this schedules include; the suitability of the lecture schedule with the IES and IE undergraduate curriculum at Mataram State Islamic University, the appropriate educational background of lecturers with their courses, and the timeliness of class schedule so that it would not interfere with regular lectures. Likewise, each class is provided with an attendance list and a lecture journal.

However, regarding face-to-face lectures models and independent learning models with time allocations on Fridays, Saturdays, and Sundays, these lecture schemes and models not only make it difficult for students to understand lecture material that 'sometimes' has to take lectures from morning to evening with different courses, but also lecturers who are 'forced' by circumstances to complete the material according to the existing plan and schedule. This resulted in the lecturers only pursuing the completeness of the material, but not in terms of the depth material. Actually, this problem can be reduced by distributing lecture modules early.

The maximum effort of lecturers in learning was admitted by DMS students, they are very competent. This is equivalent to the efforts of Manager who always tries to serve DMS students by providing a suitable teaching staff between the subjects and the academic background of the lecturers. Lecturers with all their abilities have designed the lesson so that the lecture process applies a variety of methods which 'ideally' encourage students to participate in exploring their knowledge. This results in meaningful and substantive scientific products. For example, the practice of student participation in the form of discussions, questions and answers, experiments, discoveries, deepening of material or forms of independent assignments such as compiling papers, resumes and book reviews, translation, analysis, etc.

In the assessment aspect, the value of success learning in each subject was the result of the accumulation of all the components above. If the student's ability is lack, they will be given the opportunity to attend lectures in the next semester in the remedial program.

Apart from this normative assessment model, lecturers were also not too rigid in assessing process aspects in the form of high student attendance intensity even though the distance from the location is quite far away (boarding plane for East Nusa Tenggara students), it became a separate credit point in the lecturer assessment scheme. Seeing this situation, the lecturers cannot carry out normative-authentic assessments, especially senior students. To anticipate this problem, Ministry of Religion Republic Indonesia has formulated a 'different' assessment format as a logical consequence of 'different patterns of learning activities' in order to avoid unequal assessment. This means that the assessment format and / or mark must be able to accommodate the authentic assessment variables and the assessment process.

In terms of monitoring and evaluation (Monev), both internally and externally done regularly by the Manager. Monev in this case is an activity that has purpose to monitor the progress of the DMS Program implementation. The focus of monev in this case was implemented as a tool to obtain information about the implementation of DMS program. Therefore, the focus of monev is related to the components of the program implementation process, both those related to the decision-making process, institutional management, program management, and management of the teaching and learning process of DMS Program in several lecture loci.

In general, Monev process has been effectuated routinely, but the results have not been comprehensively realized. It can be seen in the presence of students who object to the lack of budget allocation for student transportation, low salaries for DMS employees and regional apparatus due to the lack of budget allocation from the Ministry of Religion. Therefore, the monev team must reiterate so that suggestions can be accommodated and delivered to the Ministry of Religion. While this research was conducted, there had not been any changes to the transportation budget allocation and additional employee salaries.

Product Evaluation

The results of the program evaluation on the product aspect include the learning achievement component of DMS students showing extraordinary achievements. This was indicated by several indications; first, the passing rate of the courses. Referring to the documentation data, it can be seen that students who pass DMS in each subject are almost 100% in each semester. Besides, no one of DMS students repeating courses each semester. Second, the achievement of the practical dimension which is marked by the knowledge obtained by students in the lecture room can be implemented in a real learning environment. Based on the documentation data of learning practicum combined with participatory workshop activities called 'Integrated PPL-KKP', it was revealed that 100% of students passed with satisfactory grades.

In addition, the thing that needs to be further improved is the quality of the student thesis. Therefore, in the future, Management is advised to consider student involvement in social and religious activities that can be accommodated as Participatory Work Lectures or student internships. Microteaching as a program to practice teaching or implementing theory in the real class is treated as a program to improve teaching skills, which can be combined in the form of Islamic school-based lesson studies. Besides, thesis writing as a "practical subject" in conducting research and making scientific papers is a means of improving the learning process in the form of Classroom Action Research (CAR).

Outcome Evaluation

Based on the analysis of documentation and interviews with students, various institutions, and community recognition, it revealed that the results of the evaluation of the outcome aspects of DMS program had succeeded in creating 'different values' for alumni in 3 provinces in Indonesia (West Nusa Tenggara, East Nusa Tenggara, and Bali).

The success of DMS program formally was marked by an increase in the academic ability of DMS student output in the form of lesson plans preparation, teaching competence, preparation of other learning instruments, and the achievement of DMS outputs of 175 certified professional teachers at Mataram State Islamic University in Academic Year 2013-2014. However, it should be noted that the majority of DMS alumni teachers who participate in the official teacher education program and pass the certification, the majority have moderate skills, especially in the preparation of lesson plans (RPP) and professional teaching practice (according to the instruments of Ministry of Religions).

The results showed that from 175 DMS alumni who participated in the official teacher education program, only 16 people (9.14%) had the ability to make Lesson Plans (RPP) and had good teaching competencies. Most (131 people or 74.86%) were in the medium category. Furthermore, 27 people (15.43%) were in a sufficient category, and 1 person (0.57%) was in the poor category. This is very unfortunate because the government has spent a very large amount of money to make the DMS program a success.

In addition, the career development of the DMS alumni of the State Islamic University of Mataram showed a significant increase with achievements in the form of promotion, including as supervisors, headmaster of Islamic School, deputy head of Islamic school, homeroom teacher, manager of education funds, and prioritizing training such as curriculum training. For the Institutions, where DMS alumni serve, became a separate credit point for the accreditation of the relevant educational institution (in the Human Resources

component) whose teaching staff are part of this program and formally, their education and skills have increased, because they have become a bachelor's degree (S1). This DMS program has contributed to the acceleration and progress of its alumni in the provinces of West Nusa Tenggara, East Nusa Tenggara, and Bali, Indonesia.

Figure 3. Progress Report of DMS alumni formal employment

Conclusions and Suggestions

The implementation of program to improve undergraduate qualifications through DMS at Mataram State Islamic University had been done well and was in accordance with the guidelines and rules set by the Ministry of Religion Republic of Indonesia and Government Regulation No. 19 of 2005 on National Education Standards. This can be justified, both in terms of context, input, process, product, and outcome, although there are several aspects that need to be improved, such as aspects of quantity and quality.

In addition, there were several aspects that need to be improved, especially the outcome aspect such as the ability of Islamic elementary school (IES) teachers and IE teachers to guide good practice in exact learning or social lessons and in making a Lesson plan and learning competencies in educational program instruments services determined by the Ministry of Religion. In other words, Ministry of Religion in collaboration with Mataram State Islamic University jointly followed up on the significant findings of this study. The program to improve the qualification of Islamic Elementary School and Islamic Religious Education teachers through Dual Mode System should be continued. Especially in terms of aspects that have a good value such as context, input, products, and results should be maintained and improved simultaneously. However, for inadequate assessments, such as in several aspects, input, process, and results must be prioritized for handling. Further, for the process aspect should more be optimized so that the academic process and culture will have higher quality.

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